

Synthesis of Gold Nanoparticles Using Tomato Extract as Reducing Agent

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Abstract

The development of eco-friendly process for the synthesis of nanoparticle is one of the main steps in the area of nanotechnology research. This paper concerns with the green synthesis of gold nanoparticle by reducing chloroauric acid with tomato extract as reducing agent. Gold nanoparticles, GNP(T), and gold nanoparticles with stabilizer, GNP(TS), were prepared by the reduction of 0.003 M chloroauric acid (HAuCl₄) solution using different ratios of tomato extract as reducing agent and stabilized by sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) as capping agent. The reduction of gold ion was found in the formation of gold nanoparticles appearing violet-red color. The dispersion of light through the colloidal gold solution was confirmed by Tyndall effect. The synthesized gold nanoparticles were characterized by UV-visible spectroscopy. The absorption maximum at 420 nm was observed in tomato extract and GNP showed a new peak at 530 nm due to the formation of gold nanoparticle. The colloidal solution of gold nanoparticles prepared without stabilizer, GNP(T), were precipitated within two weeks while GNP(TS) in the presence of SDS were till stable for 2 months.

Keywords : gold nanoparticles, GNP, chloroauric acid, tomato extract, sodium dodecyl sulphate, green synthesis

Introduction

Nanotechnology is a field of science being still under development and has a big influence on the industry from several years. Amongst variable nanomaterials and fields of their application metal nanoparticles can be distinguished as the most popular in biology and medicine with gold (AuNPs) and silver (AgNPs) nanoparticles playing prominent role (Siemieniec, 2013). Gold nanoparticles (also known as gold colloids) of 2 nm to over 100 nm in diameter can be synthesized by controlled reduction of an aqueous HAuCl₄ solution using different reducing agents under varying conditions. Typically, gold nanoparticles display a single absorption peak in the visible range between 510 nm and 550 nm. With increasing particles sizes, the absorption peak shifts to a longer wavelength and the width of the absorption spectra is related to the size distribution range (Cai, *et. al.*, 2008). Nanoparticles can be synthesized by three methods: 1. Chemical method such as reduction (Balantrapu, *et. al.*, 2009, Tripathi, *et. al.*, 2009), 2. Electrochemical method (Rodriguez, *et.al.*, 2000) and 3. Bio-reduction method also called green synthesis (Begum, *et. al.*, 2009). However, the bio-reduction method is most widely used method as it is safer, cost effective and sustainable compared to other methods. Gardea-Torresdey, *et. al.*, (2002) were the first to report the formation of gold and silver nanoparticles inside living plants. Using plants in the biosynthesis of metal nanoparticles, especially gold and silver nanoparticles, has received more attention as suitable alternative to chemical procedures and physical methods. Bio-reduction of metal nanoparticles using a combination of biomolecules found in plant extract, *e.g.* enzymes, proteins, amino acids, vitamins, polysaccharides, and organic acids such as citrates is environmentally benign yet chemically complex. Extracts from plants may act as both reducing and capping agents in nanoparticle synthesis. The Bio-fabricated gold nanoparticles using aqueous extract of red tomato has been used as a colorimetric sensor. The water extract of the tomato juice mostly contains proteins and water-soluble organic acids like citric acid, ascorbic acid, malic acid, amino acids, and vitamins. The presence of citric acid and ascorbic

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acid in the aqueous extract of tomato juice is responsible for the reduction of gold ions while the soluble proteins and amino acids are responsible for the stabilization of GNP (Barman, *et. al.*, 2013). The stability of gold nanoparticles is a major issue which decides their impending usage in nanobiotechnological application. Often biometrically synthesized nanoparticles are deemed useless owing to their instability in aqueous medium. So, surfactants are used to stabilize the nanoparticles (Duy, *et. al.*, 2010).

In this study, the green synthesis of gold nanoparticles (GNP) was carried out by reduction of chloroauric acid solution (HAuCl_4) with various ratios of tomato extract. The gold nanoparticles were stabilized by sodium dodecyl sulphate in alkaline medium. The prepared colloidal solutions of gold nanoparticles, GNP, were characterized by Tyndall effect and UV-visible spectroscopy.

Materials and Method

Preparation of Tomato Extract

The tomato was collected from the local market and washed with deionized water. The skin was removed from the tomato. The whole mass was squeezed and filtered by using a What man filter paper. This filtrate was used as the tomato extract. The extract was diluted with distilled water to obtain different volume ratios of extract and water (10:0, 8:2, 7:3, 6:4, 5:5 and 4:6).

Preparation of Gold Nanoparticles

Gold nanoparticles, GNP(T), were prepared by the reduction of chloroauric acid solution using tomato extract. 10 mL of each of the diluted extract (10:0, 8:2, 7:3, 6:4, 5:5 and 4:6 v extract/v water) was cooled in ice-cold water and 5 mL of 0.003 M aqueous chloroauric acid was added drop wise with continuous stirring. The mixture was then cooled further for 5 min, and finally, it was heated for 10 min at 80 °C. The color of the solution gradually changed from yellow to deep reddish violet. The colloidal solutions of gold nanoparticles, GNP (T) were obtained. After carrying out above procedure, 10 mL of 0.003 M alkaline sodium dodecyl chloride (SDS) (pH=9.5) was added to the as-prepared GNP and heated at 80 °C for 5min to prepare gold nanoparticles with stabilizer, GNP(TS) (Barman. *et. al.*, 2013).

Characterization of Gold Nanoparticles

The formation of gold nanoparticles (GNP) was confirmed by the Tyndall effect. A laser pointer was taken and wrapped a rubber band around the on-switch so it was on continuously. The laser pointer was placed to the edge of the bottles containing GNP colloidal solution and the light was passed through the solution. The observation was recorded. The laser pointer was then rotated at 90° intervals and recorded any new observations.

The UV-Visible spectroscopic analysis of tomato extract, GNP (T) and GNP (TS) were carried out by UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Confirmation of Gold Nanoparticles in Solution by Tyndall Effect

Gold nanoparticles (GNP) were synthesized by 0.003 M HAuCl_4 solution with different ratios of tomato extract and stabilized by 0.003 M sodium dodecyl sulphate solution. The prepared GNP (T) and GNP (TS) exhibits reddish-violet color in aqueous medium (Figure 1). The color appears due to the excitation of the localized surface plasmon vibrations of the metal nanoparticles.

Figure 1. Color variations of gold nanoparticles (a) without stabilizer and (b) with stabilizer

Tyndall effect is the scattering of light by particles in a mixture and it is possible to view a beam of light as it passes through a colloid or a suspension. The amount of scattering depends on the frequency of light and density of the particles. Figure 2 shows the existence of gold nanoparticles in aqueous solution (as colloids). This Tyndall effect could be evident that the colloidal had dispersed particles, making them nanoparticles.

Figure 2. Photos of optical properties of gold nanoparticles (Tyndall effect)

Characterization of Gold Nanoparticles by UV-Visible Spectroscopy

UV-Visible spectroscopy is an important tool for analyzing formation of gold nanoparticles. UV-Visible spectrum of tomato extract is shown in Figure 3. It indicated that the maximum wavelength of tomato extract is 420 nm. Figure 4 and 5 show UV spectra of gold nanoparticles absence of stabilizer, GNP (T), and gold nanoparticles with SDS, GNP (TS)

produced from various ratios of extract. The appearance of strong absorption peak centered at about 530 nm in all case. Generally, gold nanoparticles display a single absorption peak in the visible range between 510-550 nm, because of surface plasmon resonance and show heavy absorption light at 530 nm. Therefore, the appearance the strong absorption peak of synthesized gold nanoparticles agrees with the literature. Absorption band at 530 nm of GNP (TS) indicated more smooth and sharper than that of GNP (T). But the color changes of gold nanoparticle give the different absorbance value depending on tomato extract ratio. The colloidal solutions of GNP (T) are unstable and precipitated within 14 days after forming gold nanoparticle while GNP (TS) are till stable for two months. It can be suggested that surfactant is controlling the shape and size of the GNP formed. It also indicated that SDS is able to stabilize gold colloid quite efficiently.

Figure 3. Plot of absorbance vs wavelength for the tomato extract

Figure 4. Plot of absorbance vs wavelength for gold nanoparticles without stabilizer

GNP(T10) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 10:0(v/v)

GNP(T8) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 8:2 (v/v)

GNP(T7) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 7:3 (v/v)

GNP(T6) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 6:4 (v/v)

GNP(T5) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 5:5 (v/v)

GNP(T4) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 4:6 (v/v)

Figure 5. Plot of absorbance vs wavelength for gold nanoparticles with stabilizer

GNP(T10S) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 10:0(v/v) with SDS

GNP(T8S) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 8:2(v/v) with SDS

GNP(T7S) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 7:3 (v/v) with SDS

GNP(T6S) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 6:4 (v/v) with SDS

GNP(T5S) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 5:5 (v/v) with SDS

GNP(T4S) = gold nanoparticles prepared by tomato extract and water ratio of 4:6 (v/v) with SDS

Conclusion

In this paper, gold nanoparticles, GNP (T) and GNP (TS), were synthesized by the reduction of 0.003 M HAuCl_4 using tomato extract as a reducing agent and sodium dodecyl sulphate as stabilizer. Ascorbic acid present in tomato extract are to be responsible for the reduction of gold ions. The reduction of Au^{3+} to Au^0 in the formation of gold nanoparticles was observed by appearing violet-red color colloidal solution. The dispersion of light through the solution by Tyndall effect confirmed to the existence of GNP in solution.

From the analysis of UV-visible spectroscopy, the absorption maximum at 530 nm in addition to the peak found at 420 nm in tomato extract was found due to the formation of gold nanoparticles. The variations of absorbance at this peak were observed depending on the

different ratios of tomato extract. Gold nanoparticles in the absence of stabilizer, GNP (T), were unstable and precipitated within two weeks while GNP (TS) in the presence of SDS were till stable for 2 months. Thus, the extracts from tomatocan act as reducing agents in environmental-friendly synthesis method for gold nanoparticles. The surfactant of sodium dodecyl sulphate is able to stabilize gold colloid quite efficiently.

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